

FINANCIAL FUNDAMENTALS OF INDONESIAN BANKS AND MACROECONOMIC FACTORS ON STOCK PRICES: MEDIATING EFFECT OF RETURN ON ASSETS

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Abstract

Financial performance is an illustration of the company's success that has been achieved on various activities that have been carried out. Financial performance is commonly used as information in assessing ratios, which can be controlled in the future, and in predicting the production capacity of existing resources. Financial performance derived from the analysis of financial statements, then used as a tool in the decision-making process in the future. Data was collected from banking financial statements listed on the Indonesian stock exchange, covering the period 2016–2020. The findings identify that financial performance includes allowance for impairment losses (ALW), Operating Expenses and Operating Income Ratio (OEIO), Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR), Net Interest Margin (NIM), Return on Equity (ROE), Non-Performing Loans (NPL), macroeconomics, return on assets (ROA) and stock prices can improve the financial economic status in the future.

Keywords: financial fundamentals, banking sector, stock exchange, macroeconomic factors, Stock Price

1. Introduction

The condition of the capital market in Indonesia cannot be separated from various kinds of securities phenomena, one of which is stocks. As one of the investment instruments known in the capital market, shares of a company with a number of potential returns offer more attractive options when compared to the deposit interest rate offered by the bank. In reality, it is not that simple, stocks with potential profits are always accompanied by various potential risks, as the principle of investing in stock securities known as “high risk high return”, stocks always bring up various other phenomena that are deemed worthy of study. These phenomena include the rise and fall of stock prices, and the assessment of the price of a stock in determining the fair value that triggers financial decisions (Yanescha, 2022).

Banking is an important financial institution in the economy of a country. Where banking has a role as an intermediary institution that distributes funds from parties who have excess funds to be channeled to parties who lack funds. Banking is a place in various transactions that are closely related to finance, a place to save money, invest, make payments, and remittance (Rochmayasari, 2022). The progress of banking in a country can be used as a benchmark for the progress of the country itself. The more developed a country, the greater the role of banks in controlling the country. Bank profitability in the economy can be determined on a micro and macro basis (Hakim, 2017). At the micro level, profit is a determinant and is needed by every competitive banking institution. At the macro level, banks must be able to absorb negative external shocks and achieve financial system stability (Al-Homaidi et al., 2018).

Banks as third-party fund collectors have a role to provide loans in the form of credit to companies. Credit provided by banks comes from the public. The public and investors entrust their funds to invest in the banking sector. Banking has a major contribution to the economic success of the country (Mahardia, 2008). All of them, cannot be separated from their role as part of the financial system, which serves as an intermediary, in order to facilitate economic activity. In its development, banking in Indonesia is experiencing increasingly fierce competition. This situation does not only occur between conventional and Islamic banking, but also with Fintech (Tribudhi & Soekapdjo, 2019). Thus, the challenge becomes even more difficult, especially to maintain the trust of the community. For this reason, banks need to maintain performance, so that their credibility is good, but also pay attention to the risks they face (Mansyur, 2021). This study aims to analyze the fundamental factors of bank performance and macroeconomics in improving banking stability in Indonesia during the pandemic era.

2. Methodology

The data analysis technique used to discuss the problem in this research is the PLS SEM method, which is a statistical technique that allows simultaneous testing of a relatively complex set of relationships (Ghozali, 2006). The path diagram aims to determine the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable by using an intermediate variable. Path diagrams present explicit causal relationships between variables based on theory. Complex relationships can be established between one or more dependent variables and one or more independent variables. There may also be a variable that plays a dual role as an independent variable in a relationship, but it becomes the dependent variable in another relationship based on cascading causality.

In this study, the data analysis method used was structural equation modeling-partial least squares (SEM-PLS) using SmartPLS software. In its development, SEM was divided into two types, namely covariance-based SEM (CB-SEM) and variance-based SEM or partial least squares (SEM-PLS). CB-SEM developed in the 1970s pioneered by Karl Joreskog as a Lisrel software developer. Meanwhile, SEM-PLS developed after CB-SEM and was pioneered by Herman Wold (Karl Joreskog academic supervisor). The following are some examples of software from CB-SEM and SEM-PLS).

Table 1: Some Examples of Software from CB-SEM and SEM-PLS

Software CB-SEM	Software SEM-PLS
LISREL	SmartPLS
Amos	WarpPLS
EQS	PLS-Graph
Mplus	Visual-PLS
STATCAL	STATCAL

SEM-PLS is considered efficient as it can work with small sample sizes and complex models. In addition, the assumption of data distribution in SEM-PLS is relatively looser than that of

CB-SEM. Estimation with CB-SEM requires a series of assumptions that must be met such as multivariate data normality, minimum sample size, homoscedasticity, and so on. The estimation results of the two are not much different so that SEM-PLS can be a good proxy for CB-SEM. SEM-PLS can still produce estimates even for small sample sizes and deviations from the assumption of multivariate normality. SEM-PLS can therefore be viewed as a non-parametric approach to CB-SEM. In addition, when the assumptions of CB-SEM are not met, then SEM-PLS can be the right method for theory testing. If the data meets the assumptions of CB-SEM correctly, such as the minimum sample size and normal distribution, then choose CB-SEM. If not, select SEM-PLS. SEM-PLS is a non-parametric approach; can work well even for extreme abnormal data.

3. Result

3.1. Outer Model Evaluation (Measurement Model)

Convergent validity is part of the measurement model which in SEM-PLS is usually referred to as the outer model while in covariance-based SEM it is called confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) (Mahmud & Ratmono, 2013). There are two criteria to assess whether the outer model (measurement model) meets the requirements of convergent validity for the reflective construct, namely: (1) Loading must be above 0.7; (2) p-value is significant (<0.05). However, in some cases, loading requirements above 0.7 are often not met, especially for newly developed questionnaires. Therefore, loading between 0.40-0.70 must be considered to be maintained.

Indicators with loadings below 0.40 should be removed from the model. However, for indicators with loadings between 0.40 and 0.70, we should analyze the impact of the decision to delete these indicators on average variance extracted (AVE) and composite reliability. The indicator can be removed with a loading between 0.40 and 0.70 if the indicator can increase the average variance extracted (AVE) and composite reliability above its limit (threshold). The limit value of AVE is 0.50 and composite reliability is 0.7. Another consideration in removing indicators is their impact on construct content validity. Indicators with small loadings are sometimes maintained because they contribute to construct validation.

Figure 1: Testing Validity based on Loading Factor

Based on the validity test of loading factors in Table 2 and Figure 1, it is known that all loading values are > 0.7 , which means that they have met the validity requirements based on the loading value. Furthermore, validity testing is carried out based on the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value. The recommended AVE value is above 0.5 (Mahmud & Ratmono, 2013). It is known that the entire AVE value is > 0.5 , which means that it has met the validity requirements based on the AVE. Furthermore, reliability testing is carried out based on the composite reliability (CR) value.

Table 2: AVE, Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha
BI RATE	0.672	0.836	0.773
OEOI	0.629	0.764	0.742
ALW	0.652	0.781	0.756
STOCK PRICE	0.662	0.823	0.761
INFLATION	0.631	0.776	0.753
LDR	0.602	0.754	0.722
EXCHANGE RATE	0.686	0.876	0.811
NIM	0.665	0.824	0.763
NPL	0.623	0.761	0.738
ROA	0.677	0.859	0.781
ROE	0.655	0.801	0.759

The recommended Composite Reliability (C.R) value is above 0.7 (Mahmud & Ratmono, 2013). It is known that all CR values are > 0.7 , which means that they have met the reliability requirements based on CR. Furthermore, reliability testing was carried out based on Cronbach's Alpha (CA) values. Then, the discriminant validity test was carried out using the Fornell-Larcker approach. Table 3 presents the results of discriminant validity testing.

Table 3: Discriminant Validity Testing

Variables	BI RATE	OEOI	ALW	STOCK	INFL	LDR	EXCH	NIM	NPL	ROA	ROE
BI RATE	1.000										
OEOI	-0.118	1.000									
ALW	-0.206	-0.048	1.000								
STOCK PRICE	0.064	0.017	-0.048	1.000							
INFLATION	0.454	-0.251	-0.295	0.201	1.000						
LDR	0.166	-0.046	-0.086	0.043	0.129	1.000					
EXCHANGE RATE	0.370	0.126	0.125	0.346	-0.459	-0.032	1.000				
NIM	0.127	-0.318	0.079	-0.174	0.335	-0.124	-0.275	1.000			
NPL	-0.080	0.388	0.454	-0.023	-0.032	-0.199	-0.05.7	-0.112	1.000		
ROA	0.185	-0.883	0.077	-0.048	0.303	-0.037	-0.164	0.548	-0.368	1.000	
ROE	0.145	-0.674	0.086	-0.099	0.282	0.017	-0.190	0.536	-0.224	0.822	1.000

In discriminant validity testing, the value of the square root of the AVE of a latent variable is compared with the correlation value between the latent variable and other latent variables. It is known that the square root value of AVE for each latent variable is greater than the correlation value between the latent variable and other latent variables. So it is concluded that it has met the requirements of discriminant validity.

3.2. Inner Model: Hypothesis Testing

Table 4 presents the results of the significance-influence test. The results showed that BI Rate has a significant effect on stock prices, with $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$. This means that the hypothesis stating that BI Rate has a significant effect on stock prices is empirically supported. Thus, the first hypothesis is accepted.

The results showed that inflation has a significant effect on stock prices, with $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$. This means that the hypothesis stating that inflation has a significant effect on stock prices is empirically supported. Thus, the second hypothesis is accepted. Moreover, the exchange rate has a significant effect on stock prices, with $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$. This means that the hypothesis stating that exchange rate has a significant effect on stock prices is empirically supported. Thus, the third hypothesis is accepted.

In examining OEOI, the results showed that OEOI has a significant effect on ROA, with p-value = 0.000 <0.05. This means that the hypothesis stating that OEOI has a significant effect on ROA is empirically supported. Thus, the fourth hypothesis is accepted. In addition, NIM has a significant effect on ROA, with p-value = 0.000 <0.05. This means that the hypothesis stating that NIM has a significant effect on ROA is empirically supported. Thus, the fifth hypothesis is accepted.

Statistical analysis also showed that ROE has a significant effect on ROA, with p-value = 0.000 <0.05. This means that the hypothesis stating that ROE has a significant effect on ROA is empirically supported. Thus, the sixth hypothesis is accepted. Furthermore, hypothesis testing also revealed that BI Rate has a significant effect on ROA, with p-value = 0.029 <0.05. This means that the hypothesis stating that BI Rate has a significant effect on ROA is empirically supported. Thus, the seventh hypothesis is accepted. The results also showed that ROA has a significant effect on stock prices, with p-value = 0.041 <0.05. This means that the hypothesis stating that ROA has a significant effect on stock prices is empirically supported. Thus, the eighth hypothesis is accepted. In examining NIM, the results showed that NIM has a significant effect on stock prices, with p-value = 0.045 <0.05. This means that the hypothesis stating that NIM has a significant effect on stock prices is empirically supported. Thus, the ninth hypothesis is accepted.

Table 4: Hypothesis Testing

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	STDEV	O/STDEV	p
BI RATE -> Stock price	-1.004	-1.002	0.114	8,814	0.000
Inflation -> Stock price	1.232	1.234	0.139	8,840	0.000
Exchange rate -> Stock price	1.266	1.268	0.095	13.261	0.000
OEOI -> ROA	-0.576	-0.584	0.107	5.400	0.000
NIM -> ROA	0.154	0.158	0.037	4.198	0.000
ROE -> ROA	0.303	0.295	0.081	3.740	0.000
BI RATE -> ROA	0.112	0.109	0.05.1	2.187	0.029
ROA -> Stock price	0.502	0.533	0.245	2.051	0.041
NIM -> Stock price	-0.184	-0.195	0.091	2.012	0.045
LDR -> ROA	-0.081	-0.078	0.041	1.959	0.051
NPL -> ROA	-0.105.	-0.100	0.060	1.742	0.082
OEOI -> Stock price	0.306	0.314	0.182	1.680	0.094
LDR -> Stock price	0.112	0.108	0.076	1.480	0.140
Exchange rate -> ROA	-0.064	-0.065	0.046	1.403	0.161
ALW -> ROA	0.074	0.069	0.059	1.257	0.209
ROE -> Stock price	-0.146	-0.157	0.121	1.208	0.228
NPL -> Stock price	0.077	0.083	0.092	0.837	0.403
ALW -> Stock price	-0.071	-0.075	0.085	0.836	0.403
Inflation -> ROA	-0.031	-0.030	0.05.1	0.596	0.552

However, the results showed that LDR has no significant effect on ROA, with p-value = $0.051 > 0.05$. This means that the hypothesis stating that LDR has significant effect on ROA is not supported by empirical evidence. Thus, the tenth hypothesis is rejected. The results also showed that NPL has no significant effect on ROA, with p-value = $0.082 > 0.05$. This means that the hypothesis stating that NPL has significant effect on ROA is not supported by empirical evidence. Thus, the eleventh hypothesis is rejected. Moreover, OEOI has no significant effect on stock prices, with p-value = $0.094 > 0.05$. This means that the hypothesis stating that OEOI has significant effect on stock prices is not supported by empirical evidence. Thus, the twelfth hypothesis is rejected.

In examining the effect of LDR on stock prices, the results showed that LDR has no significant effect on stock prices, with p-value = $0.140 > 0.05$. This means that the hypothesis stating that LDR has significant effect on stock prices is not supported by empirical evidence. Thus, the thirteenth hypothesis is rejected. Additionally, the exchange rate has no significant effect on ROA, with p-value = $0.161 > 0.05$. This means that the hypothesis stating that the exchange rate has significant effect on ROA is not supported by empirical evidence. Thus, the fourteenth hypothesis is rejected. The results also presented that ALW has no significant effect on ROA, with p-value = $0.209 > 0.05$. This means that the hypothesis stating that ALW has significant effect on ROA is not supported by empirical evidence. Thus, the fifteenth hypothesis is rejected.

The hypothesis testing also showed that ROE has no significant effect on stock prices, with p-value = $0.228 > 0.05$. This means that the hypothesis stating that ROE has significant effect on stock prices is not supported by empirical evidence.

Thus, the sixteenth hypothesis is rejected. The results also showed that NPL has no significant effect on stock prices, with p-value = $0.403 > 0.05$. This means that the hypothesis stating that NPL has significant effect on stock prices is not supported by empirical evidence. Thus, the seventeenth hypothesis is rejected. In examining the effect of ALW, the empirical evidence showed that ALW has no significant effect on stock prices, with p-value = $0.403 > 0.05$. This means that the hypothesis stating that ALW has significant effect on stock prices is not supported by empirical evidence. Thus, the eighteenth hypothesis is rejected. Lastly, the results showed that inflation has no significant effect on ROA, with p-value = $0.552 > 0.05$. This means that the hypothesis stating that inflation has significant effect on ROA is not supported by empirical evidence. Thus, the nineteenth hypothesis is rejected.

Table 5: Coefficient of Determination (R-Square)

Dependent Variables	R Square
Stock Price	0.655
ROA	0.911

As an additional analysis, the results in Table 5 showed that R-Square value of the stock price of 0.655. This means that all independent variables of ALW, OEOI, LDR, NIM, ROE, NPL, inflation, exchange rate, and BI rate are able to explain the stock price of 65.5 percent of ROA. The R-Square value of ROA is 0.911. This means that ALW, OEOI, LDR, NIM, ROE, NPL, inflation, exchange rate, and BI rate are able to explain ROA of 91.1 percent.

4. Conclusion

The findings identify that financial performance includes allowance for impairment losses (ALW), Operating Expenses and Operating Income Ratio (OEOI), Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR), Net Interest Margin (NIM), Return on Equity (ROE), Non-Performing Loans (NPL), macroeconomics, return on assets (ROA) and stock prices can improve the financial economic status of bank in Indonesia in the future.

This finding is important to consider for investors to consider the condition of the capital market in Indonesia and the financial performance of banking stock securities. Investment banking instruments are widely recognized and well established in the capital market with a number of potential returns offering stable and competitive options. In addition, investors are also expected to be aware of high-risk and high-returns by continuing to consider fundamentally the potential gains of stocks and a thorough assessment of potential risks.

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